

1 **INDUCED LACTATION IN DAIRY EWES**

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5 Response to lactation induction by estradiol and progesterone was evaluated in Lacaune and
6 Manchega ewes. In experiment 1 (winter), all Lacaune and only 21% of Manchega ewes were
7 induced into lactation. Milk yield of the induced Lacaune was only 49% of that produced after
8 lambing. In experiment 2 (spring), Manchega ewes were induced into lactation with or
9 without bovine somatotropin. Manchega ewes had an improved response in spring compared
10 to winter. Moreover, milk yield increased by 98% in bovine somatotropin-treated ewes.
11 Lactation induction had better results in Lacaune than in Manchega ewes, and during spring
12 than during winter.

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INDUCED LACTATION IN DAIRY EWES

Response to Lactation Induction Differs due to Season of Year and Breed of
Dairy Ewes

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ABSTRACT

Lactation artificially induced (ART) by steroid hormones and natural lactation (NAT) after lambing were compared in 2 dairy sheep breeds (Manchega and Lacaune) in 2 experiments conducted during winter and spring. In Experiment 1, ART ewes (14 Manchega and 9 Lacaune) were induced into lactation in winter by the standard protocol that consisted of s.c. injections of estradiol and progesterone administered in 2 portions daily from d 1 to 7. Hydrocortisone acetate was injected s.c. daily on d 18 to 20. Milking was initiated on d 21 and continued for 13 wk. A similar group of NAT ewes was selected for the contemporary comparison of NAT versus ART lactation. All Lacaune ewes but only 3 of the 14 Manchega ewes (21%) were successfully induced into lactation. Despite the successful induction of lactation in Lacaune ewes, milk yield was much lower than that obtained in NAT lactation (1.23 ± 0.14 vs. 2.51 ± 0.15 L/d; $P < 0.001$). Milk composition from wk 5 to 13 did not differ between groups, except for whey protein which was greater in ART than in NAT ewes (1.47 vs. 1.25%; $P < 0.05$). In Experiment 2, 19 Manchega ewes were divided into 2 groups and induced into lactation in spring by using the standard induction protocol similar to that used in Experiment 1 (control, $n = 9$), or the standard protocol modified with bovine somatotropin (bST, 250 mg/ewe on d 11; $n = 10$). Manchega ewes had an improved response to the standard protocol of lactation induction in spring compared to winter. Milk yield in bST-treated Manchega ewes was 98% greater than in control ewes (402 ± 85 vs. 203 ± 86 mL/d; $P < 0.10$). The use of bST during mammogenesis did not affect milk composition. In conclusion, marked differences between Manchega and Lacaune dairy ewes were observed in their response to lactation induction using the standard protocol during different photoperiod conditions. The Manchega ewes were unable to establish lactation in winter but were able to do so in spring. The response to lactation induction in dairy ewes seems to be related with

51 their endogenous levels of prolactin and growth hormone, the use of which should be
52 explored more deeply in future research.

53 **Key Words:** lactation induction, somatotropin, milk composition, dairy ewes

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INTRODUCTION

56 Hormonal induction of lactation in ruminants contributes to the understanding of lactation
57 physiology and, potentially, will be useful in reducing unproductive periods in intensive dairy
58 management systems. Numerous attempts to induce lactation with ovarian steroids (Cowie et
59 al., 1952; Smith and Schanbacher, 1973; Salama et al., 2007) have resulted in variable success
60 rates (58 to 80%) and milk yields (50 to 106% of natural lactation). Moreover, the use of large
61 doses of estrogen has led to side effects such as the undesirable exhibition of estrus behavior
62 over prolonged periods (Smith and Schanbacher, 1973) and has affected fertility negatively
63 (Salama et al., 2007).

64 To improve the response of cows, ewes, and goats to the induction treatment, researchers
65 have added placental lactogen (Byatt et al., 1997; Kann et al., 1999), somatotropin (Kann,
66 1997; Kann et al., 1999; Kensinger et al., 2006), prostaglandins (Lukas et al., 2003), reserpine
67 (Collier et al., 1977; Kensinger et al., 1979; Salama et al., 2007), and thyroid hormones (Hart
68 and Morant, 1980; Head et al., 1980). The effects reported by using reserpine, a prolactin
69 releaser, suggest that differences in the response to lactation induction occur due to season of
70 year and photoperiod sensitivity of the animals.

71 Most studies of lactation induction in sheep have been conducted using Prealpes du Sud
72 ewes (Head et al., 1980; Kann, 1997; Kann et al., 1999), which is a dual-purpose local French
73 breed and not a true dairy sheep, or local dairy ewes of a non-specified breed (Alifakiotis et
74 al., 1980). Kann (1997) and Kann et al. (1999) concluded that the inclusion of growth
75 hormone in the induction protocol is necessary to improve milk yield in ewes.

76 To our knowledge, no studies have been conducted to evaluate the results of induced
77 lactation in specified dairy sheep breeds in which a greater success rate and milk yield should
78 be expected. Moreover, little is known about differences in milk composition in dairy ewes
79 that have been artificially or naturally induced to lactate.

80 The aim of this study was to compare the lactational response to hormonal treatment for
81 lactation induction in ewes of 2 dairy breeds that differ in their productive potentiality.
82 Induced lactation by the standard protocol proposed by Smith and Schanbacher (1973) was
83 compared to natural lactation during winter (experiment 1) and this standard protocol was
84 compared to a modified protocol with bovine somatotropin (**bST**) in spring (experiment 2).

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MATERIALS AND METHODS

87 The experimental procedures and animal care conditions were approved by the Ethics
88 Committee of Animal and Human Experimentation of the Universitat Autònoma de
89 Barcelona (Reference CEEAH 606/2006).

90

Animals and Treatments

91
92 **Experiment 1.** A total of 46 ewes from 2 dairy breeds that differ in milk production
93 potential (Manchega, medium yield, n = 28; Lacaune, high yield, n = 18), were used to study
94 the response to lactation induction by a standard protocol based on the use of steroid
95 hormones. During winter, 23 dairy ewes were artificially (**ART**) induced into lactation
96 (Manchega, n = 14; 9 nulli- and 5 multi-parous; and, Lacaune, n = 9; 4 nulli- and 5 multi-
97 parous) and compared to 23 dairy ewes naturally (**NAT**) lambed (Manchega, n = 14; 9 primi-
98 and 5 multi-parous; and, Lacaune, n = 9; 5 primi- and 4 multi-parous) at the experimental
99 farm of the SIGCE de la Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona in Bellaterra, Spain (41° 30'
100 North and 2° 5' East).

101 To eliminate the possible effect of the reproductive state of the ewes on the response to
102 hormones used to induce lactation, ART ewes were estrus synchronized (starting January 23)
103 by insertion of a polyurethane vaginal sponge that contained 40 mg of fluorogestone acetate
104 of for 12 d (Chronolone, Intervet, Salamanca, Spain), and 400 IU of pregnant mare serum
105 gonadotropin (Foligon, Intervet) i.m. injected at the time of sponge withdrawal. Five days
106 after sponge withdrawal, ewes were induced into lactation by using the standard protocol of
107 Smith and Schanbacher (1973) based on daily s.c. injections of estradiol-17 β (0.5 mg/kg BW)
108 and progesterone (1.25 mg/kg BW) in 2 portions at 0800 and 1800 h from d 1 to 7. Lactation
109 was triggered by hydrocortisone acetate (50 mg/d) injected s.c. daily for 3 d (d 18 to 20).
110 Milking was initiated on d 21 (February 28) and continued for 13 wk.

111 The NAT groups of ewes naturally lambed from each breed for use in the contemporary
112 comparison of NAT vs. ART lactation were selected from the dairy flock of the SIGCE
113 according to lambing dates. The NAT ewes were mated after synchronization by ram effect,
114 lambed on February 22 (\pm 5 d) and suckled their lambs for 4 wk. Milking was initiated after
115 weaning the lambs at 27 d of age (March 21) and continued for 154 d (22 wk). Animals and
116 treatments used in Experiment 1 are summarized in Table 1.

117 **Experiment 2.** Most of the ART Manchega ewes used in Experiment 1 failed to establish
118 lactation (milk yield < 0.2 L/d). All of them were dried off for 44 ± 1 d, and re-used in a
119 second induction experiment in which a modified protocol with bST was used. To permit
120 steroids to clear the body, a period of 68 d was allowed between the last steroid injection in
121 Experiment 1 and the first steroid injection in Experiment 2. Four new nulliparous and 1
122 multiparous non-pregnant Manchega ewes were included in the experiment.

123 Manchega ewes (n = 19) were divided into 2 groups in early spring, estrus synchronized
124 via vaginal sponges (starting April 10) and induced into lactation by the same standard
125 protocol used in Experiment 1 or by the same protocol in which bST was included.

126 Ewes of the standard protocol were used as a control (Control: 6 nulli- and 3 multi-parous).
127 Ewes of the modified protocol were injected s.c. with a single dose of prolonged-release bST
128 (Lactotropina, 250 mg/ewe) on d 11 (bST: 7 nulli- and 3 multi-parous). Animals and
129 treatments used in Experiment 2 are also summarized in Table 1.

130

131 *Hormones*

132 Steroid hormones for lactation induction were supplied by Sigma-Aldrich (Sigma-Aldrich
133 Química, Barcelona, Spain). Estradiol-17 β , progesterone, and hydrocortisone acetate were
134 dissolved in dimethyl sulfoxide (USP grade DMSO, Gaylord Chemical Co., Slidell, LA) to
135 give concentrations of 1003, 44, and 245 g/L, respectively. Solutions were protected from
136 light and stored at room temperature. Insulin syringes (1 mL, BD Medical-Diabetes Care, San
137 San Agustín del Guadalix, Madrid, Spain) were used for estradiol and hydrocortisone acetate
138 injections.

139 The bST (Lactotropina) was supplied by Elanco Animal Health Mexico (Guadalajara,
140 Jalisco, México) as syringes of 500 mg of zinc bovine somatotropin and stored at 4°C until
141 their use. Each bST syringe was measured and carefully marked in order to use one half for
142 each ewe (250 mg/ewe).

143

144 *Feeding and Management Conditions*

145 Ewes grazed for 6 h daily on an Italian ryegrass pasture and were fed indoors with
146 dehydrated Italian ryegrass hay ad libitum (12% CP; as fed) and 0.5 kg alfalfa pellets (17%
147 CP; as fed). Ewes were milked twice daily (0800 and 1700 h) in a double-12 stall parallel
148 milking parlor (Westfalia-Separator Ibérica, Granollers, Spain) provided with individual
149 feeders, head lockers, recording jars (2 L \pm 5%), and a low milk pipeline. A total of 0.6 kg/d

150 commercial concentrate (6.4 MJ NE_L/kg and 16% CP; as fed), was distributed in 2 portions at
151 the a.m. and p.m. milkings.

152 Milking machine was set at a vacuum pressure of 42 kPa, a pulsation rate of 120
153 pulses/min, and a pulsation ratio of 50%. Milking routine included machine milking, stripping
154 before cluster removal, and teat dipping in an iodine solution (P3-cide plus, Henkel Hygiene,
155 Barcelona, Spain).

156

157 *Sample Collection, Analyses, and Measurements*

158 Milk yield in the lactation induced ewes was recorded daily during the first wk of lactation
159 and thereafter weekly until wk 13 (Experiment 1) or wk 5 (Experiment 2) of lactation. No
160 data were available for NAT ewes from wk 1 to 4 in Experiment 1 because they were
161 suckling their lambs. Consequently, comparison between NAT and ART ewes in Experiment
162 1 was based on data collected from wk 5 to 13.

163 Milk composition was evaluated daily during wk 1 (Experiment 1) and biweekly through
164 wk 13 (Experiment 1) and wk 5 (Experiment 2). Milk samples of approximately 100 mL were
165 collected individually and preserved with an anti-microbial tablet (Bronopol, Broad Spectrum
166 Micro-tabs II, D&F Control Systems, San Ramon, CA) at 4°C until analysis. Unhomogenized
167 milk samples were analyzed with a near infrared spectrometer (Foss NIRSystems 5000,
168 Hillerød, Denmark) for content of TS, fat, protein ($N \times 6.38$), true protein and CN (Albanell et
169 al., 1999). Whey protein was calculated by difference between true protein and CN, and NPN
170 was calculated by the difference between protein and true protein.

171

172 *Statistical Analyses*

173 Data were analyzed by the MIXED procedure for repeated measurements of SAS (SAS
174 9.1; SAS Inst. Inc., Cary, NC). The statistical mixed model contained: the random effect of

175 the animal within the treatment (NAT vs. ART, in Experiment 1; control vs. bST, in
176 Experiment 2); the fixed effects of treatment, parity and week of lactation; the interaction
177 between treatment and week of lactation, and between treatment and parity; and the residual
178 error. For Experiment 2, a group effect (ewes previously induced in Experiment 1 vs. ewes
179 induced for the first time in Experiment 2) was added to the model. Differences were detected
180 by PDIF test and significance was declared at $P < 0.05$ unless otherwise indicated.

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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

183 Doses of estradiol and progesterone used in the present study were comparable to dosages
184 previously used in ewes (Head et al., 1980; Kann et al., 1997) and goats (Chillard et al., 1986;
185 Salama et al., 2007), but were 5 times greater than those used in dairy cows (Smith and
186 Schanbacher, 1973; Collier et al., 1977). However, the ratio between estradiol-17 β and
187 progesterone (1:2.5) used in our study was the same as that used in goats and cows.

188 As a consequence of the high level of estrogens used, ewes showed signs of prolonged
189 estrus behavior during the 2 wk after the induction treatment while udders began to fill with
190 mammary secretions. Similar behavior was observed in cows (Smith and Schanbacher, 1973)
191 and goats (Salama et al., 2007).

192

193 *Experiment 1*

194 **Milk Yield.** Response to the lactation induction treatment during winter differed between
195 Manchega and Lacaune ewes. Most Manchega ewes (79%) failed to be induced into lactation
196 (only 2 nulli- and 1 multi-parous of 14 ewes produced more than 200 mL/d in wk 2 of
197 milking) with the standard protocol used, whereas all Lacaune ewes were successfully
198 induced to lactate (all ewes produced more than 400 mL/d at wk 2). A daily milk yield of 200
199 mL was taken as a criterion for lactation induction success according to the ICAR (2005)

200 minimum standard quantity of milk for milk recording in dairy sheep. To our knowledge, this
201 is the first study showing a marked difference in the response to lactation induction due to
202 genetic differences.

203 Lacaune dairy ewes yield more milk than Manchega ewes under the same management
204 conditions (Molina et al., 2001; Marie et al., 2002), which implies that a different
205 physiological milieu exists in each breed. Cows of high genetic merit produce more milk and
206 had higher concentrations of plasma growth hormone than cows of low genetic merit (Kazmer
207 et al., 1986; Westwood et al., 2000). Previous studies in Prealpes du Sud ewes, which is a low
208 milk-yielding breed, showed that the inclusion of growth hormone in the induction protocol
209 improved success rate and milk yield (Kann et al., 1999). Fernández et al. (1995) showed a 34
210 to 53% increase in milk yield of Manchega dairy ewes treated with bST in the range of 80 to
211 240 mg/ewe during lactation. Hormone levels, hormone receptors, transcription factors, or
212 other factors that are involved in seasonal productive processes in the Lacaune ewes might
213 have allowed them to respond better to the induction treatment, and consequently the need of
214 growth hormone in the induction protocol might be greater in Manchega than in Lacaune
215 ewes. We can not rule out the possibility that if Lacaune ewes had been treated with bST
216 during the induction treatment, they would have yielded more milk.

217 In this experiment ART Manchega ewes were dried-off and lactational performance
218 comparison between NAT and ART was only possible for Lacaune ewes (Figure 1).

219 At all weeks, differences in milk yield between NAT and ART Lacaune ewes were
220 significant ($P < 0.001$) and, on average (wk 5 to 13), ART ewes yielded 49% the quantity of
221 milk produced by NAT ewes (1.23 ± 0.14 vs. 2.51 ± 0.15 L/d; $P < 0.001$). This percentage
222 falls within the range of 25 to 50% reported by Head et al. (1980) in Prealpes du Sud and
223 showed that lactation induction was only partially satisfactory.

224 Milk yield decreased ($P < 0.001$) in NAT ewes from first milk recording after the weaning
225 of the lambs at wk 5 (2.82 ± 0.16 L/d) to 2.20 ± 0.16 L/d at wk 13 of lactation, showing 89%
226 per month coefficient of persistency. In ART ewes, milk yield increased gradually from wk 1
227 (0.51 ± 0.15 L/d), peaked at wk 8 (1.10 ± 0.16 L/d) and then slightly decreased to wk 13 (0.97
228 ± 0.15 L/d; $P = 0.310$) of induced lactation. Monthly persistency coefficient from the peak
229 was 91%. Similar to our work, peak milk yield during induced lactation was at wk 9 to 11 in
230 dairy cows (Collier et al., 1975), wk 7 in ewes (Head et al., 1980) and wk 9 to 10 in dairy
231 goats (Salama et al., 2007). The delayed peak in ART ewes could be an indicator of continued
232 mammary proliferation (Fowler et al., 1991) and differentiation (Fleming et al., 1986;
233 Chilliard et al., 1986) during the first 2 mo after the start of lactation.

234 There were no differences in milk yield between nulli- (1.04 ± 0.19 L/d) and multi-parous
235 (1.00 ± 0.21 L/d) Lacaune ewes in the ART group. Nevertheless, multiparous NAT ewes
236 produced more milk than primiparous NAT ewes (2.95 ± 0.21 vs. 2.08 ± 0.18 L/d; $P < 0.01$).
237 One may expect a greater response to induced lactation in multi- than in nulli-parous ewes, as
238 multiparous ewes should have had more secretory cells exposed to the hormonal treatment.
239 However, it seems that the induction treatment resulted in the activation of a similar number
240 of cells regardless of parity number in ART ewes. On the other hand, consecutive pregnancies
241 in multiparous animals resulted in a higher number of activated mammary secretory cells than
242 primiparous animals that lambd once.

243 ***Milk Composition.*** Milk composition on the first day of induced lactation (d 21) in ART
244 Lacaune ewes averaged: TS, 16.5%; fat, 4.02%; protein, 8.52%; CN, 3.85%; whey protein,
245 4.66%; and, NPN, 0.48%. Milk composition changed dramatically during the first week of
246 lactation in ART ewes as shown in Figure 2.

247 Compared to colostrum, whey protein, most of which is Ig, was low in the first day
248 secretion and represented only 55% of total milk protein. Caja et al. (2006) reported that whey

249 proteins account for 72% of total protein in the normal colostrum of goats. Consequently, the
250 first secretion obtained on d 21 from the induced Lacaune ewes did not fully mimic normal
251 colostrum. Smith et al. (1971) obtained a fluid nearly identical to colostrum on d 17 of
252 treatment in cows. The low whey proteins content, and thus, an implied low Ig content, of the
253 first secretion in our results might be a consequence of the corticoids treatment. Winger et al.
254 (1995) showed that IgG concentration in cow milk peaked on d 15 of lactation induction
255 treatment and then decreased gradually, and that dexamethasone injection triggered sharp
256 decreases in IgG concentrations in mammary secretions. The decrease in IgG concentrations
257 after dexamethasone injection might be due to decreased IgG transfer into the mammary
258 gland, dilution by increased milk secretion, or a combination of these 2 factors (Winger et al.,
259 1995). First milking was done in our case on d 21 and dexamethasone had been injected daily
260 from d 18 to 20, which may explain why this secretion differed from normal colostrum.

261 Milk protein and CN percentages in ART Lacaune ewes were high during the first 2 d of
262 lactation, decreased by d 3 ($P < 0.05$) to standard milk values and remained constant
263 thereafter (Figure 2). Similar changes were reported in induced nulliparous dairy goats
264 (Salama et al., 2007). On the other hand, milk fat and TS values stabilized later than milk
265 protein and CN, and from d 7 onwards these values were constant (Figure 2).

266 Despite the large and significant difference between NAT and ART Lacaune ewes in milk
267 yield, there were no differences in milk composition from wk 5 to 13 (Table 2; Figure 2),
268 except that whey protein was greater in ART than in NAT ewes. Similarly, the composition of
269 milk from induced lactation was not different from milk from lactations that followed
270 parturition in dairy cows (Narendran et al., 1974) and dairy goats (Chilliard et al., 1986). The
271 lack of differences between groups in the main milk components suggested that induction
272 treatment resulted in less mammary cell hyperplasia than pregnancy-initiated lactation;
273 however, the biosynthetic capacity of the cells was similar.

274 Values for the CN : Protein ratio in both groups were lower than expected for standard ewe
275 milk (74 to 77%; Molina et al., 2001; Marie et al., 2002), and were greater ($P < 0.05$) in NAT
276 than in ART ewes (Table 2). Salama et al. (2007) also reported that milk of goats induced to
277 lactate contained a lower CN : Protein ratio than milk of normal lactating goats. The low CN:
278 Protein ratio in NAT ewes may be a consequence of the negative energy balance observed
279 during early lactation in Lacaune ewes under similar feeding conditions (Molina et al., 2001;
280 Marie et al., 2002).

281

282 *Experiment 2*

283 **Milk Yield.** The Manchega ewes that responded poorly to the standard protocol in Experiment
284 1 during winter (success rate, 21%), responded much better in Experiment 2 conducted during
285 spring. Milk yields in the first 2 wk of lactation were greater than 200 mL/d for 14 of 19 ewes
286 (success rate, 74%). Success rate of lactation induction did not differ ($P = 0.510$) between
287 control (67%, 6 of 9 ewes) and bST-treated (80%, 8 of 10 ewes) ewes, or between nulli- and
288 multi- parous ewes, although the nulliparous ewes had a higher numerical success rate (69 vs.
289 33%, respectively; $P = 0.111$). This result might indicate different response to the same
290 dosage of hormones depend on whether the ewe experienced pregnancy before the induction
291 treatment or not. Bridges and Byrnes (2006) reported that previous reproductive experience
292 reduces circulating 17β -estradiol and prolactin levels in rats, and affects the estrogen-
293 mediated processes beyond first lactation. Nulliparous rats were more sensitive than
294 multiparous to lower doses of estradiol benzoate, whereas multiparous rats were more
295 responsive to the higher doses.

296 Increased success rate of lactation induction in Experiment 2 might be a consequence of an
297 improvement in the hormonal milieu in Manchega dairy ewes during spring. Lactation
298 induction for Experiment 2 was conducted in April, under increasing photoperiod conditions

299 after the spring equinox, whereas the induction in Experiment 1 was in January, close to the
300 winter solstice. Kensinger et al. (1979) showed that dairy cows induced into lactation in
301 spring had greater basal levels of prolactin and milk yields than those induced in winter.
302 Moreover, Kann (1997) reported that ewes exposed to a long day photoperiod had greater
303 plasma concentrations of prolactin, growth hormone, and IGF-1, which may result in a
304 hormonal milieu during spring that promotes greater mammogenesis and lactogenesis. The
305 importance of prolactin for mammogenesis was shown by Salama et al. (2007) who reported
306 that goats treated with reserpine (used as a prolactin releaser around the spring equinox)
307 produced 28% more milk yield than goats induced to lactate without reserpine.

308 Despite the improved success rate, response to lactation induction in Manchega ewes
309 during spring was still considered unsatisfactory. When the criterion for lactation induction
310 success was increased to milk yield > 500 mL/d, success rates were 11 and 60% in control
311 and bST treated ewes, respectively ($P < 0.05$).

312 Milk yield after lactation induction was 98% greater in bST treated ewes than in control
313 ewes (402 ± 85 vs. 203 ± 86 mL/d; $P = 0.096$, Figure 3). The difference between groups
314 might have been greater if ewes were induced under short-day photoperiod conditions. Kann
315 (1997) reported that milk yield enhancements due to the use of human growth hormone-
316 releasing factor in a lactation induction protocol in ewes were 31 and 148% during long- and
317 short-day photoperiods, respectively. Obtained results suggest an important role for prolactin
318 and bST in the response to lactation induction in dairy sheep.

319 Peak milk yield values of artificially induced Manchega ewes in Experiment 2 occurred
320 earlier (wk 2, Figure 3) than in Experiment 1 (wk 8, Figure 1) or reported in literature (wk 8
321 to 11). Peak milk yield values for control and bST ewes (Figure 3) were only 21 and 32% of
322 the peak values observed in contemporary Manchega ewes lactating naturally after lambing in
323 the same herd (Figure 1). This may be the result of an interrupted or incomplete proliferation

324 or differentiation of the secretory mammary epithelial cells in lactation-induced ewes. Milk
325 yield decrease in control ewes after wk 2 (Figure 3) was unexpected. The use of bST after the
326 start of lactation induction, as reported by Magliaro et al. (2004) in cows, might be a solution
327 to maintain and increase milk yield in Manchega ewes induced to lactate. Response of milk
328 yield and milk composition to bST doses of Manchega dairy ewes was evaluated by
329 Fernández et al. (1995).

330 ***Milk Composition.*** Despite the differences previously discussed in milk yield, milk
331 composition of Manchega ewes induced to lactate, was similar in control and bST ewes
332 throughout the experimental period (Table 3). When bST was injected during an established
333 lactation in dairy ewes, milk yield increased, but milk composition was not affected (D’Urso
334 et al., 1998). However, the treatment of Manchega dairy ewes with bST during early and mid
335 lactation reduced milk protein in both stages, whereas milk fat increased during early lactation
336 but was not affected during late lactation (Fernandez et al., 1995).

337 Values of milk composition fall within the range reported for normal milk composition
338 after lambing in Manchega dairy ewes (Casals et al., 1999; Molina et al., 2001).

339

340

CONCLUSIONS

341 Significant differences between Manchega and Lacaune dairy ewes were observed in the
342 response to lactation induction using the standard protocol of Smith and Schanbacher (1973)
343 during winter, in that, Manchega ewes were unable to establish lactation. Nevertheless, milk
344 yield in Lacaune ewes induced to lactate was only one-half that of the lambed contemporary
345 ewes. Main milk components did not vary between induced and natural lactation, although
346 whey protein content and CN : protein ratio were impaired by lactation induction. Manchega
347 ewes had an improved response to standard protocol of lactation induction during spring.
348 Milk yield was improved by the use of bST during induction (pre-milking) thereby suggesting

349 a mammogenesis and lactogenic effect in sheep, although obtained milk yield attained was
350 unsatisfactory. The use of bST during mammogenesis did not affect milk composition. It
351 seems that response to lactation induction in dairy ewes was related to prolactin and growth
352 hormone levels, the use of which should be explored more deeply in future research.

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354

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449

450 **Table 1.** Breed and parity of the ewes used per treatment in the lactation induction
 451 experiments.

Breed	Parity	Experiment 1		Experiment 2	
		Natural	Artificial ¹	Control ¹	bST treated ²
Manchega	Nulli-/primi-parous ³	9	9	6	7
	Multiparous	5	5	3	3
Lacaune	Nulli-/primi-parous ³	5	4	-	-
	Multiparous	4	5	-	-
	Total	23	23	9	10

452 ¹Lactation was induced according to the standard protocol (Smith and Schanbacher, 1973) and milking started on
 453 d 21.

454 ²Lactation was induced according to the standard protocol, bST (Lactotropina, 250 mg/ewe; Elanco Animal
 455 Health Mexico, México) was injected on d 11, and milking started on d 21.

456 ³Nulliparous for ewes induced into lactation, and primiparous for ewes of natural lactation.

457

458 **Table 2.** Least square means of average milk composition in naturally or artificially induced
 459 to lactate Lacaune dairy ewes from wk 5 to 13 (Experiment 1).

Milk component, %	Lactation		SED ¹	<i>P</i> value
	Natural (n = 9)	Induced (n = 9)		
TS	15.99	15.87	0.30	0.684
Fat	6.14	5.92	0.23	0.360
Protein	4.89	4.88	0.13	0.915
CN	3.44	3.25	0.11	0.112
CN, % of protein	69.9	66.6	1.33	0.029
Whey proteins	1.25	1.47	0.08	0.018
NPN	0.20	0.17	0.04	0.357

460 ¹ Standard error of the difference.

461

462 **Table 3.** Least square means of average milk composition in Manchega dairy ewes induced to
 463 lactate with or without bST from wk 1 to wk 5 (Experiment 2).

Milk component, %	Induced lactation		SED ¹	P value
	Control (n = 9)	bST treated (n = 10)		
TS	18.14	17.49	0.70	0.377
Fat	7.69	7.36	0.59	0.952
Protein	6.20	5.98	0.34	0.536
CN	4.64	4.49	0.21	0.493
CN, % of protein	75.0	75.3	1.93	0.882
Whey proteins	1.18	1.07	0.16	0.494
NPN	0.38	0.43	0.03	0.149

464 ¹ Standard error of the difference.

465

466 **Figure 1.** Milk yield in Lacaune (●, n = 9) and Manchega (■, n = 14) dairy ewes milked after
467 the weaning of their lambs and in Lacaune (○, n = 9) dairy ewes artificially induced to lactate
468 (Experiment 1).

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471

472 **Figure 2.** Milk composition in Lacaune dairy ewes naturally (●, n = 9) or artificially (○, n =
 473 9) induced to lactate (Experiment 1). * and † indicate a difference between naturally and
 474 artificially induced ewes at $P < 0.05$ and $P < 0.10$, respectively.

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479 **Figure 3.** Milk yield of Manchega dairy ewes induced to lactate with (\blacktriangle , $n = 10$) or without
480 (\circ , $n = 9$) bST (Experiment 2).

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